

Underlying the Causes and Impact of Crime Victimization: A Study of Urban Area in Bangladesh

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Abstract

In Bangladesh, like all other countries of the world Crime victimization has become a frightening, threatening and unsettling experience for many people. This study tries to trace the causes of different kinds of crime victimization and also tries to find out its impact on victims in relation to urban environment. Based on literature relate to victimization and collecting primary data from urban area's victim, this study will enable researchers to explore the prevalence of crime in urban area and to identify the causes and impact of crime victimization on victims by analysing the demographic status of victim-offender, measuring the causal variables and several cost likely financial, physical etc. The subject of this study was composed of 3957 respondent's selected from 12th city corporations including Dhaka city followed by probability sampling method for collecting information from the general peoples who have victimized. The study revealed that two-third of the offenders was unknown to the victim. The most common cause of victimization includes self-blaming (lack of awareness or carelessness) remained at the top reason, which constitutes 31 percent of the victim. This victimization has affected victims psychologically, physically and financially including several losses. The perceptions gathered through this study will helps to take important measures and strategies to ensure safe livelihood as well as increase the performance of the law enforcement agencies.

Keywords: Prevalence of urban crime, Victimization, public safety, causes of crime victimization, impact

1. Introduction and background

Since the independence crime victimization has become a major concern for most of the urban areas in Bangladesh that can be defined as the process of being victimized or becoming a victim and also referred as harm caused by human agents acting in violation of social norms (Kamruzzaman, 2015). The population who lives in the urban areas are now increasing in the world day by day (Guumus, 2004). The most phenomenal urban population growth in Bangladesh occurred during the 1961-74 inter-census period. Over 6 million people were living in urban areas constituting roughly 8.0% of the total population (BBS, 1987). Because of rapid urbanization, the growth rate of the urban population was 5.4% during 1991 (BBS, 1997) that increased to 28.6 million by 2001 (BBS, 2003). And from 2005 to 2017, the number of urban populations is increased at a high rate of 27% to 35% (Worldometers, 2018).

Public safety has become a great concerning issue for those urban areas which is the hubs for criminal activity because of weak security system and ineffective law enforcement (Baliki, 2014; Guumus, 2004). At the same time, several types of crime incidents as well as victimization including child victimization, rape or sexual attack, murder etc in urban areas caused by different factors generating a climate of fear and threat to the stability and social climate of cities. Crime rates vary depending on the regional level. Such as, Baiki

(2014) concluded that personal theft and physical and sexual assaults are more likely to take place in more urbanized areas than rural areas. A report published by National crime victim rights week resource guide (2017) showed that residents of urban areas experienced the highest rates of victimization in 2014 and about 55% victims are of rape and sexual assault.

There are different socioeconomic factors including unemployment, inequality etc that are responsible for increasing crime rates and consequently individual victimization (Baliki, 2014). On the other hand Cohen and Felson (1979) proposed that individuals whose routine activities take place largely within households would experience less victimization, and those who spend the majority of their time away from their homes would be subject to more victimization. Besides, situational and personal characteristics including decreasing rate of self control resulted in increasing the rate of property, personal, and sexual assault victimization (Franklin, et al, 2011). Another study found that poverty and community cohesion were positively associated with victimization by street crime and residential crime at the macro level. The study found that community cohesion increased the chance of residential crime victimization, and residential mobility was not significantly associated with criminal victimization (Roh, Kim, and Yun, 2010). Another study has conducted by Shafi in 2010 within Dhaka city in which author concluded that there remains a close relationship between the crime, violence, and the socio-economic situation of Dhaka city.

However, the incidence of crime victimization, create a direct impact on economic and social life in urban areas by interfering the individual's ability to perform across a variety of roles, including those related to parenting, intimate relationships, and occupational and social functioning. Crime victimization is associated with several physical and psychological health problems, resulting in widespread treatment needs and substantial costs to both the victim and society (Hanson, et al. 2010). Another study conducted by Canadian research centre (Oct, 05) which argued that victimization touch not only the victim but also the victim's immediate family and next of kin, neighbours, and acquaintances. The effects of victimization much hit the poor, the young, the powerless, the disabled and the socially isolated. It costs financial loss as well as physical loss, emotional loss etc. Many victims of violent crime are found to go along with the high levels of physiological anxiety, rapid heart rate, hyperventilation, and stomach distress. Crime victims often experience cognitive symptoms of anxiety, helpless, guilty, or out of control (Wasserman and Ellis, 2010).

However many studies have done in different countries about crime and victimization but few specific studies have done in Bangladesh. After a long period of independence, still, now the availability of official information about the issue of victimization is very inadequate (Hadi, 2005). There is no research paper in Bangladesh about the causes and impact of crime victimization in Bangladesh which prone to create the fear of crime among people. This study has done to find out the process of crime victimization for which people fear about to be victimized in Bangladesh. This particular work is considered to be the pioneer one in its field. The information from the victims will help understand the performance of the criminal justice agencies as well as their perception of the institution. It is also expected that the findings from the study would create a platform to discuss the investigation process and police interventions more precisely.

2. Objectives of the study

The present study objectives have been developed which is to identify the causes and impact of crime victimization. The study has been designed to collect perception from the respondents about the causes and impact related with different kind of crime victimization in urban area. The following objectives, therefore, formulated to answer the research questions. The objectives of the study are:

1. To explore the prevalence of crime in urban area.
2. To find out the relationship between victim and offender by analysing demographic status.
3. To describe the causes of crime victimization based on victim's experience.
4. To identify the impact of crime victimization on urban area's victim.

3. Conceptual framework

The study is basically an explorative work that intends to reveal the causes and nature of crime victimization in different urban area of Bangladesh.

Figure: Conceptual framework of the study

The workflow of the above figure describes the complete research process. It mainly highlights the objectives and study methodology of this study.

At the beginning of the study process, victims' perceptions about ways or causes of victimization and impact of victimization on victim have been explained by different indicators. These factors are investigated in the process of the study following victimization surveys, face to face interviews. The entire process is completed by quantitative analysis. After completing the data analysis of the study, it is found that the finding of the study is socio-demographic characteristics; lack of security; ethical problem; legal problem, attitude problems etc are responsible for victimizing others. Victimization occurs much through threatening ways which create impact on victims physically and economically.

4. Methodology

4.1 Research type

This research has assumed as Exploratory. For exploring the facts, a victimization survey in eight Divisional Cities has been taken place as a primary source of information. The respondents of the study are people residing in the selected city corporations and major districts. In this study, the quantitative crime victimization survey method at the household level is applied.

4.2 Study population

Questionnaires related to victimization survey helped to identify the respondents who have been victims of crimes against persons or property. The crime screening technique ensured that only the ones that have been victims of a crime could respond to questions related to them. The total household of the study areas is 29, 73,645 (BBS, 2011) distributed among 12 city corporations and two major cities. A general household survey is conducted based on a pre-structured questionnaire which separated the victims from the non-victims.

4.3 Sample selection

The research has followed the survey method for data collection. All twelve city corporations and two major rising cities were selected as the study area. The selected cities were clustered according to distribution, and the number of wards was selected randomly using a clustered sampling technique from

each city. All the households of the selected wards were treated as the sampling unit of the study. Households were selected from the wards by a systematic random sampling technique. A screening questionnaire was used for interviewing victims of crime.

Crime victims were the target population, though the general household survey has been conducted where households were considered as the unit of analysis. Households were selected from the wards by a systematic random sampling technique. A screening questionnaire was used for interviewing victims of crime. Two-stage screenings were conducted using the research questionnaire. First, the respondents were approached, and the enumerators will record general information, and then if they are found a victim of crime the enumerators will continue the survey and completed the questionnaire; if found not victim, the enumerators skipped the rest part of the questionnaire and went for another household.

While surveying if the enumerator finds any multiple numbers of crime victims at a single household, then they are supposed to cover all of them if they qualify the condition to be a respondent of the study.

The following statistical formula is used to estimate the minimum sample size:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{The sample size, } n &= \frac{z^2 p (1-p)}{d^2} * \text{def} \\ &= \frac{(1.96)^2 (0.5)(0.5)}{(0.02)^2} * (1.5) \\ &= 3601 \end{aligned}$$

(3640 for equal distribution of respondents into selected areas)

Where n is the estimated minimum sample size

z = the value of standardized normal variate = 1.96 at 95% confidence level

p = Anticipated population proportion = 0.5

d = Absolute precision = 2%

def = Design effect = 1.5

As the size of the population is large, therefore, to ensure the validity and reliability, the original sample size has been determined by using design effect, 1.5. Considering, **z=1.96, p=0.5, d=0.02; the minimum sample size is 3601**. In order to minimize human errors and refusal of the respondents, the absolute precision level has been increased. In that case, the total sample size would be **3601**. Therefore, a total of **3640 (for equal distribution into 14 cities) respondents are statistically come up from the 8 division 14 cities, i.e., 260 from each city**.

To maintain randomness, at least five wards were selected from each of the cities which were selected based on the rate of the propensity of victimization, and then 1 Mahalla will be selected randomly from which the respondents will be selected using systematic sampling technique from each ward. The proportionality characteristic of the population was not used as it does not bear any statistical significance for representing the victim or their rate within the total number. Due to the unavailability of victim data in the total population, the random sampling method here is more logical. However, the probability sampling method has been followed for collecting information from the general peoples who have victimized and have a fear of crime.

While approaching the respondents, the enumerators also looked for victims other than the respondents who first came in contact. As a result, other victims from the same household also were covered, which increased the total number of respondents. The current total number of respondents is 3,957. Multiple responses in the sense of multiple victimization information have also been considered in the study.

4.4 Data collection

The study team has designed and developed a structured and standardized survey questionnaire for data collection. Data were collected from the systematically selected samples. In this victimization survey design, the researcher used a structured survey questionnaire containing both open-ended and close-ended questions with multiple response options. The researcher used a direct face-to-face interview technique with the completed questionnaire. Public consultation helped the researcher to find out the mass view on the variables. A total number of 3,957 respondents' information was collected while multiple responses found common in most of their responses.

4.5 Data Processing

Quantitative data were collected from the study areas. The data were processed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software and Microsoft Excel software. The qualitative data were coded and then tabulated. Some types of qualitative responses needed to be pre-coded, and others were post-coded. Data were analyzed with both descriptive and inferential statistical tools like frequency distribution, cross-tabulation, central tendency. Various types of statistical charts are used for the presentation of findings. Univariate, bivariate, and multivariate statistical analysis are used. Different forms of tests have been performed to analyze the data.

5. Findings and discussion

High victimization rate because of several crimes in urban areas than rural areas has become a concerning issue for Bangladesh. So, causes or ways and impact related to victimization are central point of this study. This study aimed at identifying the individual who have victimized already and know about their victimization process. For this reason this study has been divided into some parts such as profiling the demographic status of victim and offender, causes of victimization by exploring the several ways followed by criminal to attack victim and its impact on victims who have affected physically even financially.

5.1 Profiling of Victims and Victimization

5.1 .1 Socio-Demographic Profile of the Victims

The total picture of the sample can be understood from the household data. Besides this, to get a more precise look into the victims' information, we have provided a brief description of the victims' demography here.

Firstly, the rate of women victimization is more than the male, as the data shows females constituted 53 percent and males 47 percent. The next question comes with their age. The study showed that the average age of the victims is about 36 years, where the minimum age considered for the study was 12, and the highest age of the victim was 86. The study also showed that about 60 percent of the victims were ranged from 20 to 40 years of age. People from 40 to 50 years aged also had a significant victimization rate (about 17 percent).

Figure 1: Age Group of the Victims

Bangladesh has Muslim domination on its demography, which also was represented in the study as it showed about 90 percent of the victims were Muslim. The victims' educational background is essential because it influences their consciousness about the crime environment around them as well as the propensity to not fall for prey to crime. However, a strong correlation has been observed here in the case of victims' education level and rate of victimization. It is found from the study that about 74 percent of the victims had a less than graduation level of educational background, where 31 percent had secondary to higher secondary certificate degree. People with a higher education level had a less victimization rate (post-grad about 11% and grad about 15 percent).

Figure 2: Family Income of the Victim

In terms of occupation, homemakers had the highest number of victimization (about 37 percent), business people had the next higher rate (about 20 percent) followed by service holders (17 percent). About 40 percent of the victims' income ranged from 10,000.00 to 20,000.00.

The study also showed that people who have less than 40,000 taka as family income has a higher propensity to become the victim (about 77 percent). The data shows that people with a higher family income have a lower propensity to become a victim of crime.

5.2 Profile of the Perpetrators

The involvement of offenders in the victimization is vital to understand the victimization process in Bangladesh. The process of victimization may include victim-offender relationships, as well as the offender's age, education and occupation, etc.

5.2.1 Number of Offenders Involved in the Crime

At the incidents, the presence of multiple offenders has a direct impact on the victims' fear of crime and also post-traumatic disorders. The study found at least one offender was involved in the highest 34 percent of the incidents, two to three offenders were involved in about 20 percent of the cases, 4 to 5 offenders were involved in about 10 percent of the cases, 6 to higher offenders were involved in only about 5 percent of the cases. About 29 percent of the cases, the victim could not identify the number of offenders as it happened in the dark or at night.

5.2.2 Offenders' Age

Half of the victims could not specify the age of the offender. However, about 16 percent of the offender's age was 20 to 25, about 8 percent were found to be around 28 to 30, offenders of above 35 to 40 constitute more than 10 percent, the rest of the offenders were aged ranging 40 to 70.

5.2.3 Sex of the Offender

According to the victims of crimes, all most all of the offenders were male (62.8 percent, while 33.6 percent couldn't be identified). Only 3 percent were females, and six third gendered people were found to be involved.

5.2.4 Education of the Offender

The study found that at least in 153 cases, the offenders' background was known to the victim, where about 30 percent of the offenders were illiterate, and about 35 percent had primary and secondary education. The study also shows that the more the offender is educated, the less they are the offender. Education has a direct influence on human action proved again.

Table 1: Offender's Educational Qualification (if known)

Level	Frequency	Percent
Illiterate	46	30.1
Primary	28	18.3
Secondary	26	17.0
SSC	22	14.4
HSC	12	7.8
Graduation / Hon's	16	10.5
Post-Graduation	3	2.0
Total	153	100.0

5.2.5 Offender's Place of Residence

According to the survey, more than 54 percent of the victim thinks the offender lives in their areas or adjacent to their location. A significant number of victims shared that they think the offenders live in the neighbourhood areas. About 23 percent of the victims think that the offenders come from the outside of the town area.

Table 2: Offender's Place of Residence (if known)

	Frequency	Percent
Own Area of the Victim	78	25.49
Nearby Area of the Victim	52	16.99
Adjacent to Home of the Victim	38	12.42
Neighbourhood Area of the Victim	43	14.05
Village	3	0.98
Outside of Town Area	70	22.88
Own Home	13	4.25
At Slam	9	2.94
Total	306	100.00

5.3 Prevalence of Crime

The propensity of crime differs based on the nature of the residence as well as the crime prevention strategies used by law enforcement agencies and their activeness. Just like the previous perception of crimes at the residential level, the study also found some traditional nature of the crime in those areas. For example, theft has always remained the major social and law enforcement problem, which also found to have a strong connection with drug-related offences. Snatching items while travelling has also been a problem for the passengers of rickshaw and CNG run auto-rickshaw.

Table 3: Crime Propensity

Crime Type	Frequency	Percent
Theft	754	60.5
Burglary	7	.6
Snatching	93	7.5
Robbery	5	.4
Dacoity	8	.6
Extortion	24	1.9
Forgery	4	.3
Cheating	12	1.0

Bribery	5	.4
Damage of Property	33	2.6
Illegal Trespass	7	.6
Illegal Confinement	20	1.6
Threatening / Showing Fear	26	2.1
Violence against Women	4	.3
Child Abuse	2	.2
Attempt to Murder	2	.2
Sexual Harassment	17	1.4
Abduction	1	.1
Hurt	3	.2
Grievous Hurt	2	.2
Acid Throwing	1	.1
Human Trafficking	1	.1
Riot	3	.2
Drug-Related Offence	161	12.9
False Case	2	.2
Harassment	5	.4
Assault	4	.3
No problem	24	1.9
No Comment	16	1.3
Total	1246	100.0

5.4 Causes of crime victimization

The causation of crime has been studied from the victim's perspective, where the question for causation remained open, and their responses were coded later. In the following table, the responses are presented exactly like the victims' opinions. The most common cause of victimization both from man and woman perspective was self-blaming remained at the top reason, which constitutes 31 percent of the victim. The victims also blamed the lack of security (16 percent) for crime occurrence at their places. Around 16 percent of victims shared that their physical weakness, social status, corrupted social system, absence of a guardian, etc. impedes the probability of crime occurrence.

Table 4: Gender wise Causes of Victimization (n=1209)

Type of Responses		Gender of the Respondents			Total
		Male	Female	3rd Gender	
Don't Know	Count	28	41	0	69
	% within the causes	40.6%	59.4%	0.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	2.3%	3.4%	0.0%	5.7%
Self-Blaming	Count	176	202	0	378
	% within the causes	46.6%	53.4%	0.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	14.6%	16.7%	0.0%	31.3%
Lack of Safety and Security	Count	73	121	0	194
	% within the causes	37.6%	62.4%	0.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	6.0%	10.0%	0.0%	16.0%
Fraud/ Breach of Trust/	Count	25	12	0	37
	% within the causes	67.6%	32.4%	0.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	2.1%	1.0%	0.0%	3.1%
Drug Addiction	Count	25	40	0	65
	% within the causes	38.5%	61.5%	0.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	2.1%	3.3%	0.0%	5.4%

Abuse of Political Power	Count	20	3	1	24
	% within the causes	83.3%	12.5%	4.2%	100.0%
	% of Total	1.7%	0.2%	0.1%	2.0%
Breach of Trust	Count	16	14	0	30
	% within the causes	53.3%	46.7%	0.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	1.3%	1.2%	0.0%	2.5%
Masculinity attitudes towards women	Count	55	54	0	109
	% within the causes	50.5%	49.5%	0.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	4.5%	4.5%	0.0%	9.0%
Vulnerability of Minority Groups / Weakness of Law & Social System / Absence of Guardian	Count	49	41	0	90
	% within the causes	54.4%	45.6%	0.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	4.1%	3.4%	0.0%	7.4%
Clash between groups / enmity of victim with perpetrators / lust / Obstruction or forceful possession of offenders	Count	64	81	0	145
	% within the causes	44.1%	55.9%	0.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	5.3%	6.7%	0.0%	12.0%
Refusal of Love	Count	0	2	0	2
	% within the causes	0.0%	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	0.0%	0.2%	0.0%	0.2%
Bribery/ swindling/ forgery/ extortion/ corruption/ fraud	Count	14	12	0	26
	% within the causes	53.8%	46.2%	0.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	1.2%	1.0%	0.0%	2.2%
Criminal Mind of the individual	Count	5	4	0	8
	% within the causes	55.5%	44.50%	0.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	0.4%	0.3%	0.0%	0.7%
Illegal Arrest/ Police Arrest for doubt	Count	2	1	0	3
	% within the causes	66.7%	33.3%	0.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	0.2%	0.1%	0.0%	0.2%
Dowry	Count	1	7	0	8
	% within the causes	12.5%	87.5%	0.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	0.1%	0.6%	0.0%	0.7%
Differential Association	Count	12	8	0	20
	% within the causes	60.0%	40.0%	0.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	1.0%	0.7%	0.0%	1.7%
Total	Count	565	643	1	1209
	% within the causes	46.7%	53.2%	0.1%	100.0%
	% of Total	46.7%	53.2%	0.1%	100.0%

Figure 3: Causes of the Victimization

5.5 Ways of victimization

The general type of victimization in this study occurred from theft, wherein most of the cases, the victims did not have to confront the offender. But the other offences had victim-offender contact at the scene. As per the study outcome, 259 victims out of 1246 had contact with the offender, which is about 21 percent, among them 19 percent of the victims faced a direct threat or attempt to hurt or at least got a forceful push by the offender. More than 15 percent of the victims got the threat of attack (other than rape and murder), another 15 percent faced armed threats, and about 14 percent got the threat of murder, which affects the victims’ level of fear of crime. The threat of sexual harassment and eve-teasing found comparatively less in this study. It must be noted here that due to common perceptions and media report people might have expected to get a higher number of sexual victimization rate from this study which it does not portrays because the nature of the study and the participants were mostly adult though it counted victims above 12 years old, it did not encounter those victims through the study.

Table 5: Process of attacking Victim

Type of Attack	Frequency	Percent
Threat of rape	5	1.9
Threat of murder	37	14.3
Threat to attack (other than rape and murder)	40	15.4
Threat of sexual harassment (other than rape)	7	2.7
Eve teasing	8	3.1
Unwanted sexual contact without force	4	1.5
Threat with arms	38	14.7
Attempt of attack with a knife or sharp object	35	13.5
Attempt of attack with other arms (except sharp object)	8	3.1
Throwing an object at the victim	6	2.3
Stalking	10	3.9
Attempt to hurt or push	49	18.9
Harassment	12	4.6
Total	259	100.0

5.6 Impact on victims

5.6.1 Physical impact on Victim:

The study further investigated the victims’ experience at the crime to learn the type of injuries they suffered from it. It appears that different forms of assault are prevalent in this case. Only 132 of 1246 victims shared about their sufferings, which account for 10.6 percent.

Table 6: Type of Injury Suffered by Victim

Type of Injury	Frequency	Percent
Attempt to murder	6	4.5
Raped	1	.8
Attempt to rape	1	.8
Sexual assault other than rape or attempted rape	9	6.8
Knife or stab wounds	22	16.7
Wounds from stick blow	23	17.4
Wounds from wrestling	25	18.9
Internal injuries	7	5.3
Knocked unconscious	4	3.0
Bruises, black eye, cuts, scratches	16	12.1
Swelling, chipped teeth	7	5.3
Assault by Police	2	1.5
Head injury	2	1.5
Mental Torture	3	2.3
Assault	1	.8
Harassment	1	.8
Burnt injury	1	.8
Broken bones or teeth knocked out	1	.8
Total	132	100.0

5.6.2 Treatment received by the victim:

Among the 132 victims, about 74 percent of them had to take different forms of treatment, which originally accounts for 8 percent of the total victims. About 40 percent of the victim took first aid treatment at home and near the medicine shop, while about 24 percent had to go to the emergency room for taking immediate treatment.

Table 7: Places from where Treatment Taken by Victim

Treatment Taken At	Frequency	Valid Percent
At the scene	1	1.0
At home	21	21.4
First aid centre	18	18.4
Doctor's chamber/health clinic	18	18.4
Emergency room at hospital / clinic	23	23.5
Hospital (other than the emergency room)	15	15.3
At Local Medicine Shop	2	2.0
Total Suffered	98	100.0

5.6.3 Financial impact on victim

Victimization can be calculated by monetary value as the victim always suffers certain types of loss, which could be both psychological and physical. These losses can be calculated as property loss, medical cost, legal service cost, income loss, productivity loss, relocation cost, any other cost affected due to the crime in comparison to prior victimization. The study reveals that the highest amount of loss ranges from 100 to 20,000 taka, and theft alone constitutes about 53 percent. The next crime type is snatching, which has also been reported as the cause of loss of up to 20,000 taka. The table also shows that the loss amount to more than 1, 00,000 is also significant, which happened through damage of property, forgery, and cheating.

Table 8: Cost of Crime

Types of Crime	Cost of Crime									Total
	100-10000	10000-20000	20000-30000	30000-40000	40000-50000	50000-60000	60000-100000	100000 +	Others	
Assault	1 12.5%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	1 12.5%	0 0.0%	1 12.5%	1 12.5%	4 50.0%	8 100.0%
Harassment	1 7.7%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	1 7.7%	1 7.7%	1 7.7%	9 69.2%	13 100.0%
Domestic Violence	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	2 100.0%	2 100.0%
Harassment by Police	2 18.2%	6 54.5%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	2 18.2%	0 0.0%	1 9.1%	11 100.0%
Land related lawsuit	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	1 12.5%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	6 75.0%	1 12.5%	8 100.0%
False Case	1 25.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	3 75.0%	0 0.0%	4 100.0%
Drug Related Offence	13 40.6%	0 0.0%	2 6.3%	1 3.1%	2 6.3%	2 6.3%	1 3.1%	1 3.1%	10 31.3%	32 100.0%
Arson	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	1 50.0%	1 50.0%	0 0.0%	2 100.0%
Grievous Hurt	4 57.1%	1 14.3%	2 28.6%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	7 100.0%
Hurt	6 50.0%	3 25.0%	0 0.0%	1 8.3%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	1 8.3%	0 0.0%	1 8.3%	12 100.0%
Sexual Harassment	10 29.4%	1 2.9%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	1 2.9%	0 0.0%	22 64.7%	34 100.0%
Attempt to Murder	1 25.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	1 25.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	2 50.0%	0 0.0%	4 100.0%
Rape	1 100.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	1 100.0%
Child Repression	1 100.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	1 100.0%
Women Repression	7 28.0%	1 4.0%	2 8.0%	0 0.0%	3 12.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	4 16.0%	8 32.0%	25 100.0%
Threatening / Showing Fear	13 17.8%	21 28.8%	1 1.4%	0 0.0%	1 1.4%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	4 5.5%	33 45.2%	73 100.0%
Illegal Confinement	9 42.9%	2 9.5%	1 4.8%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	1 4.8%	5 23.8%	3 14.3%	21 100.0%
Illegal Trespass	4 36.4%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	1 9.1%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	6 54.5%	11 100.0%
Damage of Property	2 2.7%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	1 1.4%	4 5.4%	0 0.0%	4 5.4%	60 81.1%	3 4.1%	74 100.0%
Bribery	22 66.7%	1 3.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	7 21.2%	0 0.0%	1 3.0%	2 6.1%	0 0.0%	33 100.0%
Criminal Breach of Trust	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	2 22.2%	0 0.0%	2 22.2%	4 44.4%	1 11.1%	9 100.0%
Cheating	21 30.0%	11 15.7%	3 4.3%	2 2.9%	2 2.9%	2 2.9%	5 7.1%	21 30.0%	3 4.3%	70 100.0%
Forgery	2 10.0%	0 0.0%	2 10.0%	2 10.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	2 10.0%	12 60.0%	0 0.0%	20 100.0%
Extortion	17 58.6%	3 10.3%	1 3.4%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	1 3.4%	1 3.4%	5 17.2%	1 3.4%	29 100.0%
Dacoity	6 15.8%	6 15.8%	0 0.0%	1 2.6%	3 7.9%	0 0.0%	7 18.4%	13 34.2%	2 5.3%	38 100.0%
Snatching	46 35.1%	51 38.9%	9 6.9%	2 1.5%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	16 12.2%	1 0.8%	6 4.6%	131 100.0%
Theft	211 36.8%	149 26.0%	38 6.6%	20 3.5%	37 6.5%	10 1.7%	29 5.1%	49 8.6%	30 5.2%	573 100.0%
Total	401 32.2%	256 20.5%	61 4.9%	31 2.5%	63 5.1%	17 1.4%	76 6.1%	195 15.7%	146 11.7%	1246 100.0%

Out of 1246 respondents, 1100 respondents came up with a rough calculation about the cost of crime while they suffered. The total cost of crime for 1100 respondents was in total: 36, 92, and 50,260. The average cost of crime: 3, 35,682.05

Conclusion

Urban crime and victimization has become an important concern for local governments and policymakers. More victimization rate is creating more fear and stress among people who cannot lead normal life after victimization. No victims in the world want to be victimized willingly. Such as sexual assault victims do not choose to be raped; parents do not raise their children to be murdered; and women do not get married to be abused. Situation pushes them to be victimized. Various factors or cause are related with victimization such as Bashar & Islam, (2021) showed that poverty and improper law are the main causes of child victimization. Teresia, (2011) argued that youth employment is a major causes of urban violence. Besides Baliki, (2014) & Guumus, (2004) showed in their report that only because of weak security system and ineffective law enforcement urban area has become a centre of criminal activity. Canadian Resource Centre for Victims of Crime argued the impact of criminal victimization as serious fact because of several emotional, physical, psychological and financial impacts on victims.

This study has therefore conducted the first-ever crime victimization survey on the victims who are at least 12 years old and became a victim of crime within last one year from 12 city corporation and 2 other cities of Bangladesh. This study is one of the pioneering attempts in Bangladesh. The primary objectives were to explore the prevalence of crime in urban area and to identify the causes and impact of crime victimization on victims by analysing the demographic status of victim-offender, measuring the causal variables and several cost likely financial, physical etc. Survey methods have been adopted to conduct the study. The respondents were selected randomly and then screened based on a comprehensive survey questionnaire which has two segments: household screening and victim screening.

After reviewing different literature related with fear of crime and collecting information from primary data it is found that 259 victims out of 1246 had contact with the offender argued that they have faced a direct threat or attempt to hurt or at least got a forceful push by the offender. Two-third of the offenders was unknown to the victim. The most common cause of victimization, from both men and women's perspective, was self-blaming (lack of awareness or carelessness) remained at the top reason, which constitutes 31 percent of the victim.

On the other hand if we noticed the fact of the impact of victimization on victims then found that out of 1246 respondents, 1100 respondents came up with a rough calculation about the cost of crime while they suffered. The total cost of crime for 1100 respondents was in total: 36, 92, and 50,260—the average cost of crime: 3, 35,682.05. For all the above reasons crime victimization has become a great concerning issue. So, police should give priority first to increase the public's sense of security through launching visible protection strategies and act actively on it, like registering in and out in a particular residence or increasing monitoring system by CCTV or other technological ways, etc. Police in order to prevent crime properly need to increase their effort on spatial analysis like identifying hotspot of crime, making buffer area while after a crime take place to find the offender and also restore peace in the particular areas.

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